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Deliverable 22.1

INVENTORY OF CORE SOCIAL POLICY DATABASES AND INDICATORS FOR COMPARATIVE RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT

This InGRID deliverable is part of Work Package 22 on 'Innovative solutions for comparative policy indicators and analysis'. The purpose is to provide an inventory of core social policy databases and indicators for comparative research. We map 26 databases and infrastructures that fruitfully can be used in comparative research to analyse the causes and consequences of social policy. Each database is compared according to a set of characteristics, including type of data (expenditures, institutional indicators, beneficiary statistics, socio-economic/income surveys, microsimulation), policy areas included (cash benefits: family benefits, unemployment benefits, sickness benefits, pensions, work-accidents, social assistance, and disability/invalidity/survivors benefits; public services: child care, health care, elder care, and active labour market policy), countries and years covered, as well as interval for updating of data. Nearly all databases specialise on distinct parts of social policy, and data on cash benefits are somewhat more frequent than data on public services, particularly when institutional indicators are in focus. Compared with data on social expenditures and beneficiaries, institutional indicators are based on social policy legislation and thus independent of changes in social needs and population characteristics.

This report constitutes Deliverable 22.1 'Data inventory on core policy indicators in the area of poverty, living and employment conditions', for Work Package 22 of the InGRID project.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Context of research

The chief objective of the InGRID project (Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion) is to integrate and bring forward existing European social sciences research infrastructures in areas of poverty and living conditions, as well as in areas of working conditions and vulnerability. The project runs from February 2013 to January 2017 and involves 17 European research institutes. The InGRID community provides transnational data access, organises mutual knowledge, and improves methods and tools for comparative research. As part of Work Package 22 ‘Innovative solutions for comparative policy indicators and analysis’, this report provides an overview of existing comparative social policy databases that fruitfully can be used in cross-national research to analyse issues related to combatting poverty and strengthen social cohesion in Europe and elsewhere. The report is part of a wider set of data inventories tied to other InGRID work packages, covering different areas of welfare states.

Comparative research on social policy has attracted growing interest in recent decades, not only in academia but also in politics. The increased emphasis on comparative approaches to social policy analysis has several explanations. Major political events and processes, likewise demographic transitions and structural shifts in labor markets and macroeconomics, have certainly raised an interest for comparing alternative strategies to redistribute resources, improve welfare and promote social equality. Part of the explanation for the increased popularity of comparative social policy analysis in both academia and in public discourse is probably also more practical. It has simply become easier to access comparative social policy data due to substantial progress in research infrastructures. However, while data infrastructures have improved and made data more available for researchers and policy makers, there is an emerging need for systematic analyses that synthesise the vast amount of information that can be downloaded from the internet and used in quantitative comparative social policy research.

Our inventory of data infrastructures for comparative research in areas of social policy can be situated within the context of the inclusive growth priority of the Europe 2020 Growth Strategy and the recently outlined Pillar of Social Rights Initiative. The Europe 2020 Growth Strategy is the current steering wheel for economic and social integration of the European Union, where five ambitious objectives related to employment, innovation, education, social inclusion and climate/energy are formulated. The headline target for employment is 75% of people 20-64 years in employment by 2020. The social inclusion target is 20 million fewer people in or at risk of poverty and social exclusion. The European Pillar of Social Rights is the European Commission’s latest major initiative in the field of employment and social affairs. Once in place, it will detail a number of essential principles in policy-making that will serve as a compass for renewed convergence within the Euro area and policy discussion in the European Union as a whole. In order to monitor the Europe 2020 Growth Strategy and to inform discussions on a European Pillar of Social Rights, good measurement tools and indicators are necessary. This report contributes to this agenda by increasing awareness of good quality social policy data that readily can be used for cross-national research purposes.

1.2 Aim and structure of the report

The aim of this InGRID deliverable is to provide an overview of existing major comparative data infrastructures that fruitfully can be used to analyse social policy in European countries. We will begin our inventory by discussing different broader strategies in data collection and their implications for cross-national social policy research. Thereafter we will outline the various aspects based on which datasets will be detailed and compared. The following section provides the inventories of existing research infrastructures. In the final section, we present a short summary and discuss areas in data collection that are missing or require special attention in future developments of data infrastructures for comparative social policy research and analysis.

2. Strategies in comparative social policy data collection

2.1 Conceptualisation and measurement of social policy

The conceptualisation and measurement of social policy has attracted considerable attention in academia (Green-Pedersen, 2004), not least in relation to the debate about welfare state stagnation and retrenchment that emerged following the publication of Pierson's (1996) seminal work on the new politics of welfare states. In this supposedly new era of welfare state development beginning in the mid-1970s and characterised by fiscal austerity coupled with contentious political conflict and multifaceted social interests, social policymaking is believed to be very different from that characterizing welfare state expansion in the immediate decades following the Second World War. Instead of stressing the significance of class-based political alliances in understanding welfare reform, Pierson (*ibid*) and others (Pierson, 2001) argued that the era of welfare state retrenchment creates a distinct set of political problems that give voice to different and partly new actors, and invokes new strategies in policymaking.

The new politics perspective in comparative social policy theory building has received some empirical evidence in the literature, although results are far from conclusive. While Castles (2001), Huber and Stephens (2001), Siegel (2001), as well as Kittel and Obinger (2003) show that class-based partisan politics no longer explain developments in social policy, Korpi and Palme (2003), Allan and Scruggs (2004), Ferrarini (2006), Montanari and Nelson (2013), as well as Birnbaum et al (2017) come to the complete opposite conclusion (i.e. that politics still matter). One likely reason for these conflicting results in comparative welfare state research concerns precisely the conceptualisation and measurement of social policy. Whereas Castles (2001), Huber and Stephens (2001), Siegel (2001), and Kittel and Obinger (2003) based their empirical analyses on developments in social expenditures, Korpi and Palme (2003), Allan and Scruggs (2004), Ferrarini (2006), Montanari and Nelson (2013), as well as Birnbaum et al (2017) focused on changes in entitlement structures or levels of social provision (i.e. the degree to which social policy respond to needs that arise in different periods of life, for example due to sickness or old-age).

Although it may be tempting to dispatch conceptual problems and measurements issues to the long list of methodological obstacles surrounding social science in general and comparative social policy analysis in particular, both our concepts and measures certainly deserve more serious reflection. The ways in which social policy is conceptualised and measured have important implications, not only for theory building as noted above, but also for the empirical analysis of policy as well as the political discourse that is informed by research findings (Clason and Siegel, 2007). The number of comparative welfare state data infrastructures that can be used for social policy analysis has flourished in recent decades, providing the research community with a great variety of different types of indicators that can be used to inform policymaking and contribute to theoretical development. In a previous InGRID deliverable on comprehensive indicators for the analysis of out-of-work benefits (Doctrinal *et al.*, 2016), we distinguished and discussed the advantages and disadvantages associated with five different types of data that nowadays commonly are used in the literature; expenditures, case-load statistics, income distribution data, welfare state regime classifications, institutional social rights indicators, and microsimulations. This is not the place to engage in an exhaustive discussion of the pros

and cons of different types of indicators. Rather we will briefly recapitulate some of our previous discussion.

The main advantage of *social expenditure data* is availability. Comparative data on social expenditures are regularly updated and often readily available for cross-country research purposes. Perhaps the most obvious drawback is that social expenditures are affected by several factors besides policy design. For example, social spending typically rises in economic downturns when unemployment increases, although the design of social policy remains the same or even becomes subject to retrenchment (Kangas, 1991). *Institutional policy data* are typically based on theories about social citizenship where legislative frameworks define the rights and duties of citizens (Marshall, 1950). The major advantage of institutional data is the close resemblance to the actual content of social policies. By using institutional data, we gain a more thorough understanding of what welfare states actually intend to do for their citizens and what kind of support people should receive according to legislative frameworks (Ferrarini *et al.*, 2013). The downsides are the cumbersome task of collecting institutional data and the possibilities of revealing ‘paper realities’ (Van Oorschot, 2013). *Case-load statistics* from administrative records or *income statistics* from social surveys may here fruitfully complement the analysis by showing which types of welfare state benefits and services people actually enjoy, and how much money or in-kind support they receive in reality. However, availability of benefit recipient data is not as good as for social expenditures, and data generally suffer from program overlaps and inconsistencies in administrative categories between countries and over time (Dedeken and Clasen, 2011; 2013). The latter also characterise income survey data (Van Oorschot, 2013).

Due to the problems involved in comparative research to conceptualise and measure social policy, it is common among researchers to use a *regime-based approach* where outcomes are interpreted along the lines of broader social policy model types or institutional categories. By necessity, welfare state regime-based analyses are performed at very high levels of theoretical and empirical abstraction. Although the categorisations of countries into different welfare state regimes have provided valuable insights into the basic principles of social policy and broader cross-country patterns (see Esping-Andersen, 1990; Castles and Mitchell, 1992; Leibfried, 1992; Lödemel and Schulte, 1992; Ferrera, 1996; Bonoli, 1997; Gough *et al.*, 1997; Korpi and Palme, 1998; Korpi, 2000), the analytical grid is often too coarse for causal analysis. Nor is there any agreement about the exact number or nature of separate regimes or the categorisations of countries into different social policy model types (Arts and Gelissen, 2002). In addition, differences across countries that are grouped together are obscured, while gradual changes in policy over time are hard to observe (Ferrarini *et al.*, 2014).

One strategy that is sometimes used to overcome some of the disadvantages noted in relation to the different types of social policy data above is to rely on so-called *tax-benefit microsimulations*, which can be used to analyse effects of taxes and benefits on household incomes and work incentives. Microsimulations are widely used in government departments, academia, and by economists in the private sector to analyse the impact of changes in income tax, social security contributions, indirect taxes, social security benefits, housing benefits, and other policy variables on household incomes or some other type of micro level outcome. These calculations provide additional evidence on the winners and losers from policy variation and change (Immervoll *et al.*, 1999). One obstacle in this regard concerns the difficult task of setting up appropriate tax-benefit microsimulation models, which requires considerate investment of time and resources.

No matter which conceptual decisions and choices regarding measurement we impose on our investigations on social policy, it is important to acknowledge that we may be more or less ‘on’ or ‘off’ target. Awareness of concepts and measurements is a key factor in order for theory and empirical evidence to align and create an intelligible whole. We thus need to think carefully about the conceptual differences that lie behind our measurements, and choose the most appropriate social policy indicators that harmonise most closely to our theoretical concerns and research questions addressed. Although scholarly debates about the conceptualisation and measurement of welfare states and social policy for long were preoccupied by the idea to advocate for a particular type of data and indicators,

it is nowadays increasingly acknowledged that many of the questions raised in the literature on welfare states and social policy, their causes and consequences, require the combination of different types of data (Green-Pedersen, 2007; Kühner, 2007; Dedeken and Clasen, 2011; Van Oorschot, 2013). Thus, whereas institutional social rights data may provide a detailed account of how policies are set-up in national legislation, expenditure data, case-load statistics, beneficiary ratios and microsimulations provide additional insights on how policies work in reality when we also take population characteristics and changes in needs or social risks into consideration.

In the following, we will map a number of different databases that can be used in comparative social policy research to analyse welfare states from different perspectives and according to different benchmarks. The databases in this inventory provide examples of all major types of data noted above and can fruitfully be used in conjunction to address questions of immediate relevance for various inclusive growth strategies in areas of social policy.

3. Methodology and inventory

3.1 Selection of databases and search criteria

For this inventory, 26 comparative databases were selected based on a set of criteria. The first criterion was topical. Data should facilitate analyses on social policy, either at systemic or programmatic level. Social policy is here defined broadly as involving all kinds of cash benefits or services (in-kind benefits) that are offered through the welfare state. For this particular inventory, we excluded education from this definition. Second, data should be large-scale comparative and include more than a handful of countries. Third, data should include European countries. Fourth, data should be timely in character or updated regularly. Discontinued data infrastructures with outdated indicators were therefore excluded, although it is sometimes unclear if data infrastructures are discontinued or not. Fifth, data should be fairly well-known and have contributed to a number of peer-reviewed journal articles, thus indicating that data are of high quality and trustable. Sixth, the data infrastructures should preferably provide standardised indicators or quantitative data that are readily available for comparative analysis. Text-based databases, such as the Mutual Information System on Social Protection (MISSOC), the Social Security Programs throughout the World (SSPTW), EUR-lex, and Health Systems in Transition (HiT) were therefore excluded.

The list of databases included in this inventory is by no means exhaustive. Instead of providing a complete mapping of comparative data infrastructures in areas of social policy, our ambition is to highlight data commonly used in comparative welfare state research on European countries. Each data infrastructure is categorised by a set of criteria, such as type of data, policy programs covered, years and countries included, and intervals for updating. In addition, for each dataset we provide a brief description of the main social policy variables offered by the infrastructures.

3.2 Selected databases for the inventory

The databases included in this inventory are either established and maintained by international organisation (ILO, OECD, WHO, EU) or organised and provided free of charge by independent research projects and institutes. Table 3.1 provides an overview of the selected databases, with their full names and abbreviations. We also provide links to the internet homepages of each database. For most infrastructures, data can directly be downloaded following these links. In some cases, pre-registration is necessary. In the following, we will refer to databases by their abbreviations rather than their original names. While most of the selected databases provide users with primary data resulting from the host institutions' own data collection efforts, some infrastructures mainly compile indicators from other data providers. Such datasets, relying mainly on secondary data from other sources for their social policy indicators to varying degrees include CWS, DICE and GGP.

Table 3.1 Selected comparative databases for social policy analysis

Database	Abbreviation	Organised/carried out by	Type	Homepage
Atlas of Social Protection Indicators of Resilience and Equity	ASPIRE	The World Bank	I	http://datatopics.worldbank.org/aspire/
Benefits and Wages	BenWage ¹	The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)	I	http://www.oecd.org/social/benefits-and-wages.htm
Comparative Family Policy Database	CFPD ¹	The Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research	R	http://www.demogr.mpg.de/cgi-bin/databases/fampoldb/index.plx
Comparative Welfare Entitlements Dataset	CWED	The Department of Political Science, University of Connecticut and the Department of Political Science, University of Greifswald	R	http://cwed2.org/
Comparative Welfare States Dataset	CWS	The Center for European Studies (CES), University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill	R	http://www.unc.edu/~jdsteph/common/data-common.html
Database for Institutional Comparisons in Europe	DICE	The Leibniz Institute for Economic Research at the University of Munich (Ifo)	R	http://www.cesifo-group.de/ifoHome/facts/DICE.html
European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions	EU-SILC	The European Commission	I	http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/microdata/european-union-statistics-on-income-and-living-conditions
Family Policy Database	FPD ¹	The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)	I	http://www.oecd.org/social/family/database.htm
Generations and Gender Contextual Database	GGP	Laboratory of Population and Policy at the Max Planck Institute of Demographic Research	R	http://www.ggp-i.org/data/ggp-contextual-database
Global Health Observatory	GHO	The World Health Organization (WHO)	I	http://www.who.int/gho/en/
European system of integrated social protection statistics	ESSPROS	The European Commission	I	http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/social-protection/overview
Luxembourg Income Study	LIS	The LIS Cross-national Datacenter in Luxembourg	R	http://www.lisdatacenter.org/our-data/
Minimum Income Protection Indicators database	CSB-MIPI	The Herman Deleeck Centre for Social Policy (CSB), University of Antwerp	R	http://www.centrumvoorsociaalbeleid.be/index.php?q=node/3270
Multilinks	Multilinks	The Berlin Social Science Center	R	https://multilinks-database.wzb.eu/
Nordic Welfare Database	NowBASE	The Nordic Council of Ministers	I	http://nowbase.org/da
Social Security Inquiry	SSI	The International Labour Organisation (ILO)	I	http://www.ilo.org/dyn/ilossi/ssimain.home
Tax-benefit microsimulation model for the European Union	EUROMOD	The Institute for Social and Economic Research (ISER), University of Essex.	R	https://www.euromod.ac.uk/

Database	Abbreviation	Organised/carried out by	Type	Homepage
Hypothetical Household Tool for tax-benefit simulations in EUROMOD	EUROMOD-HHoT	The Herman Deleeck Centre for Social Policy (CSB), University of Antwerp, and The Institute for Social and Economic Research (ISER), University of Essex.	R	https://www.euromod.ac.uk/
OECD Health Database	HealthDat ¹	The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)	I	http://www.oecd.org/els/health-systems/health-data.htm
Pensions at a Glance Database	PAG	The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)	I	http://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/social-issues-migration-health/data/oecd-pensions-statistics/pensions-at-a-glance-2011_data-00625-en?isPartOf=/content/datacollection/pension-data-en
OECD Social Expenditure Database	SOCX	The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)	I	https://www.oecd.org/social/expenditure.htm
Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe	SHARE	Munich Center for the Economics of Aging (MEA), Max Planck Institute for Social Law and Social Policy	R	http://www.share-project.org/
Social Benefit and Recipients Database	SOCR	The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)	I	http://www.oecd.org/social/recipients.htm
Social Policy Indicators Database	SPIN	The Swedish Institute for Social Research (SOFI), Stockholm University	I	http://www.sofi.su.se/spin/
Tax and benefits indicators database	EC Tax Benefit ¹	The European Commission	I	http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/db_indicators/tax_benefits_indicators/index_en.htm

¹ No official abbreviation. I=International organisation. R=Research institute.

4. Comparisons and mapping of databases

4.1 Country coverage and years

Country coverage and years differ widely across the databases. Table 4.1 shows country coverage and years of the databases included in this inventory. All databases provide indicators spanning several years, but only a few infrastructures have data covering both the period of welfare state expansion in the immediate decades following the Second World War as well as the era of welfare state stagnation and retrenchment that characterise the period after the mid-1970s. Many databases are unbalanced as data for some countries and years are missing. In the table below, we indicate the maximum time span of the data.

In terms of country coverage, most databases provide information for longstanding welfare democracies (i.e. EU15 or OECD18). EU15 includes Austria, Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Sweden, and the United Kingdom. OECD18 includes Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Japan, the Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland, the United Kingdom and the United States. Country coverage tends to increase when data are provided by international organisations. Although it has become more common that databases include developments also in Central and Eastern European countries and Southern Europe, in many databases these countries are often missing for early waves of data covering developments before 1990.

Databases that are administered by international organisations often rely on national government agencies to provide raw data. However, it should be noted that some independent research groups also have managed to collect comparative social policy data for quite an impressive number of countries. For the databases surveyed in this InGRID deliverable, the number of countries ranges from 7 to over 194.

Table 4.1 Country coverage and years

Database	Country coverage	Years	Intervals
ASPIRE	120 countries (mostly low- and middle-income countries)	1998-2014	No clear interval
BenWage ¹	OECD	2001-2016	Yearly
CFPD ¹	OECD18, Greece, Luxembourg, Portugal, Spain	1960-2010	Yearly
CWED	EU27, Australia, Japan, New Zealand, South Korea, Taiwan, the United States	1971-2011	Yearly
CWS	OECD18, Greece, Luxembourg, Portugal, Spain	1960-2012	Yearly
DICE	EU28, Australia, Canada, Japan, New Zealand, Norway, Switzerland, the United States	1975-present (varies according to area of interest)	
EU-SILC	EU28, Iceland, Norway, Switzerland, Turkey	2004-2016	Yearly
FPD	OECD	1995-2014	Yearly
GGP	Australia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russian Federation, Sweden	1960-2008	Mostly yearly
GHO	194 countries	1995-2014 (varies across indicators and countries)	Yearly
ESSPROS	EU28, Iceland, Norway, Serbia, Switzerland, Turkey	1990-2014	Yearly
LIS	66 countries spanning all continents	1967-2013 (varies across countries)	Five (-2000) and three (2004-) year intervals
CSB-MIPI	EU27, Norway, United States for later waves	1992, 2001, 2009, 2012	No clear interval
Multilinks	EU27, Norway, Georgia, Russia	2004, 2009	No clear interval
NowBASE	Denmark, Faroe Islands, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden	1995-2013	Yearly
SSI	104 countries spanning all continents		
EUROMOD	EU28, Iceland, Norway, Switzerland, Turkey	1998-2015 (varies across countries)	Yearly
EUROMOD - HHoT	EU28, Iceland, Norway, Switzerland, Turkey	2009-2015	Yearly
HealthDat	OECD, Brazil, China, Colombia, Costa Rica, India, Indonesia, Lithuania, Russia, South Africa	1960-2015	Yearly
PAG	34 OECD countries	2007-2015	Two year intervals
SHARE	Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland	2004-2013	Two year intervals
SOCX	OECD	1980-2016	Yearly
SOCR	OECD, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Romania	2007-2012	Yearly
SPIN	OECD, EU27, Indonesia, Philippines, Taiwan, Thailand, Vietnam, Brazil	1930-2015	Yearly and five year intervals
EC Tax Benefit ¹	EU28	2001-2015	Yearly

Note: OECD18 includes Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Japan, the Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland, the United Kingdom and the United States. EU27 includes Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovak Republic, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden and the United Kingdom. EU28 includes also Croatia.

4.2 Type of data

As noted above, comparative research on welfare states and social policy are based on different kinds of data. In this section, we document the main type of data and indicators that are available in the databases included in this inventory. Here we distinguish between five types of data; expenditure, institutional, beneficiaries, socio-economic/income surveys, and microsimulation. In addition, we indicate whether data are provided at macro or micro levels. The macro level databases provide country level variables, whereas micro level databases provide information at individual or household levels for multiple countries. Table 4.2 shows the type of data offered by each database included in this inventory. Several databases include different types of data.

Twelve databases provide data on social policy expenditures, often disaggregated by major program types and expressed as percentages of GDP or some other common denominator. This includes ASPIRE, CWS, DICE, ESSPROS, FPD, GHO, GGP, SSI, HealthDat, NOWBASE, PAG and SOCX. ASPIRE, ESSPROS, NowBASE and SSI also provide data on the number of beneficiaries of different types of social benefits. Besides family policy expenditure, FPD also provides institutional data on entitlement levels, as well as data on child care usage. FPD also has other data on child care, such as child-to-staff ratios and minimum qualification requirements. An indicator of entitlements for a two-child family from FPD is also included in GGP. CWS and PAG also provide institutional data in the form of entitlement levels for some major cash benefit programs. For CWS this institutional data are from CWED. It should be noted that also HealthDat and GHO, in addition to health expenditures, provide institutional data on health care financing, provision (i.e. health employment, medical technology and hospital beds), and health care coverage. SOCR is a new database exclusively specialised on beneficiary statistics and it provides unique data on the number of recipients of main income replacement programs based on administrative records.

Seven databases are specifically designed to provide different types of institutional social policy data, to various degrees covering areas of financing, eligibility and entitlement levels. Included here are CFPD, CWED, CSB-MIPI, Multilinks, BenWage, SPIN, and EC Tax Benefit. Model family techniques are commonly used in many of these institutionally oriented research infrastructures to calculate entitlement levels. Based on national social policy legislation, entitlements are here calculated for pre-defined families, for example, a single person, a couple without children, a lone parent, or a dual parent household (Bradshaw *et al.*, 1993). Compared to other measures of the scope of social benefits, measurements based on model family techniques are solely influenced by how social policy is defined in national legislation, and not affected by differences in needs and population characteristics. For more information on model family techniques in comparative social policy research, see Doctrinal *et al.* (2016).

SHARE is a multidisciplinary European panel survey containing microdata on physical and psychological health among people aged 50 and over. It also contains self-reported information on several socio-economic indicators, such as income from insurance programs. EU-SILC is a European wide socio-economic survey including income statistics by benefit types. EU-SILC also includes information on child care use. LIS includes harmonised micro level income data for a large number of countries. LIS income data are disaggregated by major types of social benefit programs. Both EU-SILC and LIS can be used to analyse the number of benefit recipients or the income position of beneficiaries (see Sainsbury and Morissens, 2002; Van Oorschot, 2013). The microsimulation platform offered by EUROMOD is based on EU-SILC. EUROMOD nowadays includes a model family tool (developed within the InGRID project), which can be used to analyse entitlement structures from an institutional perspective and as expressed in national legislation. For more information on this new Hypothetical Household Tool (HHoT), see Hufkens *et al.* (2016).

It should be noted that SHARE, EU-SILC, LIS, EUROMOD, and EUROMOD-HHoT do not provide any standardised social policy indicators that can be directly downloaded and readily used for comparative analysis. Instead, users are provided access to micro level data or simulation platforms that fruitfully can be used for social policy analysis. However, both the Eurostat and LIS provide

some country level key variables on social policy, which are based on EU-SILC and LIS micro level income data.

Table 4.2 Main types of social policy data

	Expenditure	Institutional	Beneficiary statistics	Socio-economic/ Income survey	Micro-simulation	Macro/ Micro
ASPIRE	X		X			Macro
BenWage		X				Macro
CFPD		X				Macro
CWED		X				Macro
CWS	X	X				Macro
DICE	X	X				Macro
EU-SILC				X		Micro
FPD	X	X	X			Macro
GGP	X	X				Macro
GHO	X	X				Macro
ESSPROS	X		X			Macro
LIS				X		Micro
CSB-MIPI		X				Macro
Multilinks		X				Macro
NowBASE	X		X			Macro
SSI	X		X			Macro
EUROMOD					X	Micro
EUROMOD – HhoT					X	Macro
HealthDat	X	X				Macro
PAG	X	X				Macro
SHARE				X	X	Micro
SOCX	X					Macro
SOCR			X			Macro
SPIN		X				Macro
EC Tax Benefit		X				Macro

4.3 Program areas and variables

None of the databases in this inventory covers all separate parts of social policy (however defined). Table 4.3 shows the main types of programs that are separately covered in each database. One major distinction is between cash benefits and public services (sometimes referred to as benefits in kind). For cash benefits, the databases in this inventory to varying extent cover family benefits, unemployment benefits, sickness benefits, pensions, work-accidents, social assistance, disability, invalidity, and survivors benefits. Family benefits include various types of child allowances and parental leave insurance benefits, as well as subsidies for dependent spouses and fiscal child benefits. Most databases that include information on social assistance also have data on housing benefits and other types of

means- or income-tested minimum income benefits. For CSB-MIPI this also includes data on minimum wages, in-work benefits and child care fees for minimum wage families (Van Mechelen *et al.*, 2011). BenWage also includes data on child care fees and subsidies.

As regards public services, the databases in this inventory provide indicators related to child care, health care, elder care and active labour market policies. Data on public services are commonly in the form of expenditures or beneficiary ratios. Only in a few cases, particularly in the area of family policy, are data on public services oriented towards an institutional analysis of welfare states (i.e. rights as defined by national, or regional/local, legislation). It should be noted that variables in NowBASE and SSI are difficult to categorise according to the schedule in Table 4.3. In both databases, policy indicators are in some instances based on population categories (i.e. elderly, children, working age, and so forth) rather than the specific social risk categories covered by different social policy programs (i.e. sickness, unemployment, disability, etc.).

Table 4.3 Main types of social policy programs

	Cash benefits						Public services				
	Family benefits	Unemployment benefits	Sickness benefits	Pensions	Work-accidents	Social assistance	Disability/invalidity/survivors benefits	Child care	Health care	Elder care	Active labor market policy
ASPIRE	X	X	X	X	X	X	X				X
BenWage	X	X				X		X			
CFPD	X										
CWED		X	X	X	X						
CWS	X	X	X	X		X	X	X	X		X
DICE	X	X		X				X	X		X
EU-SILC	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X			
FPD	X							X			
GGP	X	X		X				X	X		
GHO									X		
ESSPROS	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
LIS	X	X	X	X	X	X	X				
CSB-MIPI	X			X		X					
Multilinks	X			X				X		X	
NowBASE	X		X	X		X	X	X	X	X	
SSI	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		X
EUROMOD	X ¹	X ¹	X ¹	X ¹	X ¹	X	X ¹	X ²			
EUROMOD – HhoT	X ¹	X ¹	X ¹	X ¹	X ¹	X	X ¹	X ²			
HealthDat									X		
PAG				X			X				
SHARE	X	X	X	X	X	X	X				
SOCX	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
SOCR		X		X		X	X				
SPIN	X	X	X	X	X	X					
EC Tax Benefit	X	X				X					

¹ Contributory benefits can in some cases only partially be simulated in EUROMOD due to incomplete work histories in EU-SILC input data.

² Can be analysed for a selection of countries included in EUROMOD by amendments developed within the ImPRovE project (Hufkens & Verbist, 2016) and the InGRID project (Hufkens & Verbist, 2017).

In order to provide a more detailed description of each dataset, Table 4.4 provides some additional information on the core social policy variables included in each database. In addition, we indicate whether data are disaggregated by family type, population subgroups or some other characteristic.

Table 4.4 Core social policy variables and disaggregation

	Variables	Disaggregation by family type, population subgroups or some other characteristic
ASPIRE	Social expenditures as percentage of GDP disaggregated by program categories. Coverage, adequacy, targeting performance, benefit-cost ratios.	Some indicators of social programs are disaggregated by rural and urban areas, by quintiles of pre/post welfare distribution, and by those living with less than \$1.25 a day.
BenWage	Net incomes of employed and unemployed model families at different earnings-levels based on model family techniques. Replacement rates including family benefits, gross employment income, housing benefits, income tax, in-work conditional benefits, social assistance/minimum benefit, social security contributions, unemployment benefits; child care allowances or tax credits.	Model families include a single person, single parent with two children; married couple without children and married couple with two children.
CFPD	Monthly allowance for each child in the family; family allowance expenditure; gross enrolment ratio in pre-primary education; value of tax and benefit transfers to a two-child family. Maternity leave prior to and after childbirth in weeks, maternity leave benefits as percentage of female wages, parental leave in weeks, parental leave benefits as percentage of female wages, total leave in weeks, total leave benefits as percentage of female wages.	Not disaggregated by family type, population subgroup or some other characteristic.
CWED	Unemployment and sickness insurance: benefit duration, coverage, qualifying conditions, replacement rates, waiting periods. Pensions: coverage; minimum and standard pension replacement rates; ratio of employee contributions to the total of employee's and employer's contributions.	Replacement rates in unemployment and sick pay insurances are calculated for two types of households: a single household and a dual parent household with one dependent spouse and two children aged 7 and 12. For pensions, two types of households are considered: a single person and a couple without work history.
CWS	Social spending, revenue and welfare state institutions data: indices of benefit generosity (overall, unemployment, sickness, pension), social expenditure (public, private, total) disaggregated by program type and expressed in national currencies and as percentages of GDP.	Not disaggregated by family type, population subgroup or some other characteristic.
DICE	Topics covered: social policy, education, labor market, migration, banking and financial markets, business. Within the social policy topic, are included data about basic protection, family policy; health, and pensions.	Not disaggregated by family type, population subgroup or some other characteristic.
EU-SILC	Topics covered: socio-demographic characteristics of respondents; education; material deprivation; health; housing; income; labor, ad-hoc modules on various topics. Includes income disaggregated by type of benefit.	Includes both individual and household level data.
FPD	General policies for families with children: public spending on family benefits and education, family cash benefits, neutrality of tax-benefit systems, child support (maintenance) systems, public spending by age of children, intergenerational solidarity, legal age thresholds, various aspects of child protection. Child-related leave: key characteristics of parental leave systems, use of childbirth-related leave benefits, additional leave entitlements of working parents, parental leave replacement rates, trends in leave entitlements. Formal care and education for very young children: public spending on childcare and early education, enrolment in childcare and pre-school, informal childcare arrangements, childcare support. Typology of childcare systems: typology of childcare and early education services, quality of childcare and early education services, out-of-school-hours care.	Some variables are disaggregated by age, sex and earnings-level.

	Variables	Disaggregation by family type, population subgroups or some other characteristic
GGP	Public spending on social protection, pensions, unemployment benefits, childcare, health care, family allowances. Childcare enrollment, health care resources, family benefit entitlements.	Not disaggregated by family type, population subgroup or some other characteristic.
GHO	Access to health care and essential medicines. Prevalence of health technology, vaccine coverage, total health expenditure, health employment.	Some variables are desegregated by sex and broader age-groups.
ESSPROS	Public expenditure on social protection benefits (cash or in-kind), disaggregated by the following functions: Sickness/health care, disability, old age, survivors, family/children, unemployment, housing, social exclusion not elsewhere classified. Supplementary modules on the number of pension beneficiaries and net social protection benefits.	Not disaggregated by family type, population subgroup or some other characteristic.
LIS	Includes income disaggregated by type of benefit.	Includes both individual and household level data.
CSB-MIPI	Includes the monetary value of minimum wages, social assistance for able-bodied working-age population, and minimum income guarantees for the elderly, and the net disposable income in each of these income situations. In addition to social assistance, housing benefits, tax credits, child allowances, and heating allowances. For the minimum wage cases, in-work benefits are included. Benefits are expressed gross and net of taxes in national currencies as well as standardised according to consumer prices, purchasing power parities, average gross wages, and median disposable household incomes. The database also includes information on conditions attached to receipt of social assistance.	Benefits are calculated for a single person, a married couple without children, a married couple with children aged 7 and 14, a lone parent with children aged 7 and 14, and a lone parent with one child aged 2.
Multilinks	Maternity and parental leave, childbirth and child-rearing allowances, leave dedicated to fathers, effective parental leave, childcare coverage rates for children under 3 years and between 3 and 5 years, care costs and opening hours, child allowances (levels and eligibility conditions), tax allowances, public income support for children, legal obligations towards children. Responsibilities to care for elderly, public care provision for older people, structure of care service provision, number of care service recipients, pension entitlements, minimum pensions, net replacement rates, recognition of care work.	Childcare costs and public income support are calculated for a couple and a lone parent at different income levels. Child allowances are calculated for one child, per child for two children, per child for three children.
NowBASE	Total expenditure on health care (national currencies and as percentage of the Gross Domestic Product), hospital beds by specialty, health employment, children enrolled in daycare by age, recipients and number of days with of daily cash benefits in the event of pregnancy, childbirth or adoption by sex, recipients of disability benefits and pensions by sex, families and pensioners receiving housing benefits by marital status, recipients of social assistance by age group, social expenditure by type (families and children, housing, survivors, elderly, disabled, social exclusion) and by type of benefits and services (families and children, unemployed, sickness, old-age and disability pensions).	Some indicators are disaggregated by age, sex and marital status.
SSI	Social benefit expenditure (old age and survivors, children, as well as working age) as percentage of GDP. Old age contributors ratio (percent of working age and labor force), old age pension recipient ratio above retirement age, unemployed receiving unemployment benefits, social and health (total and public) expenditures as percentage of GDP, percentage of health care expenditure not financed by out of pocket payments.	Not disaggregated by family type, population subgroup or some other characteristic.
EUROMOD	See EU-SILC	See EU-SILC

	Variables	Disaggregation by family type, population subgroups or some other characteristic
EUROMOD – HhoT	See EU-SILC, allows EUROMOD model family analyses	Model family analyses can be conducted for a large selection of different household types.
HealthDat	Health expenditures and financing (public and private), health care resources (employment, medical technology and hospital beds), health care utilisation (doctors and dentists consultations, immunisation, screening, hospital length of stay and discharges by diagnostic categories, diagnostic exams, surgical procedures, waiting times, long-term care resources and utilisation.	Some variables are disaggregated by sex and broader age-groups.
PAG	Public spending on old-age and survivors' pension; gross and net replacement levels; gross and net pension wealth.	Some variables are disaggregated by sex.
SHARE	Panel survey with microdata on physical and psychological health of individuals over 50 years of age. Survey questionnaires also contain questions concerning income from almost all types of social policy programs.	Contains both household and individual level data.
SOCX	Expenditures for a vast amount of social policy programs (both cash benefits and in-kind benefits) at various levels of aggregation. Expenditures are divided into public, mandatory private and voluntary private.	Not disaggregated by family type, population subgroup or some other characteristic.
SOCR	For all types of social benefits (unemployment, social assistance, disability, and old-age) the database shows the number of recipients. Reference populations; number of unemployed individuals, working-age individuals, individuals over age 65.	Not disaggregated by family type, population subgroup or some other characteristic.
SPIN	Includes seven data modules covering different social policy areas. The Social Citizenship Indicator Program, the Social Insurance Entitlements Dataset, and the Social Policy in East Asia Dataset include detailed information on replacement levels, coverage rates, eligibility criteria, and financing of four major social insurance programs (old age pensions, sickness insurance, unemployment insurance, and work accident insurance). The Out-of-Work Benefits Dataset includes net replacement rates across a great number of earnings-levels, including indicators capturing the progressivity of income replacement. The Social Assistance and Minimum Income Protection Dataset includes detailed information on the benefit position of low-income households, including levels of social assistance, housing allowances, child benefits and tax credits. The Parental Leave Benefit Dataset includes indicators on earnings-related maternity, paternity and parental leave insurance programs, whereas the Child Benefit Dataset includes detailed information on the generosity of universal child benefits, employment based child benefits, income-tested child benefits, child tax allowances, child tax credits, and child tax rebates.	Replacement rates and entitlement levels are calculated for different model families (single person, lone parent, and two parent family)
EC Tax Benefit	Includes net replacement rates of unemployment benefits and social assistance (including housing benefits), tax wedges, net increase of disposable income in moves from employment and inactivity, withdrawal of benefits (family benefits, housing benefits, in-work benefits, and social assistance).	Data are disaggregated by family type (single person, single parent, one-earner couple, one-earner couple with children) and earnings level.

5. Conclusions

This deliverable is part of the Work Package 22 ‘Innovative solutions for comparative policy indicators and analyses’ in the InGRID project (Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion). The purpose was to provide an inventory of core social policy databases and indicators for comparative research. Based on a pre-established set of criteria we have mapped 26 comparative data infrastructures and categorised them according to different criteria; including type of data, countries and years covered, programs included, as well as the usual time interval for updating the data. In addition, we provided information about key social policy variables in each database.

The list of databases in this inventory is far from exhaustive. Rather than providing a complete listing of databases, we opted to include databases that are commonly known to researchers in the field and recognised as leading infrastructures in the area of comparative social policy analysis. For the selection of databases, we used several criteria. One prominent criterion was that the infrastructures should provide quantitative data, preferably, in the form of standardised indicators that can directly be used for comparative social policy analysis. Thus, text-based analyses were excluded. Another central criterion was that the databases should be fairly up to date and regularly updated. Thus, discontinued infrastructures with ‘outdated’ data were excluded.

For ease of presentation, Table a1.1 (in appendix) shows a summary of our mapping of databases. Half of the databases in this inventory are provided by international organisations, including the European Commission, the World Bank, the World Health Organization (WHO), the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and the International Labor Organisation (ILO). The other half is provided by independent research groups or institutes. Most databases provide policy indicators for many countries and years, and are updated regularly, often on a yearly basis. However, only a few databases cover all EU Member States for an extended period in time spanning also developments of welfare state expansion in the 1960s and 1970s.

In terms of types of data, we distinguished between expenditures, institutional indicators, beneficiary statistics, socio-economic/income surveys, and microsimulation infrastructures. Twelve databases provide expenditure data on social policy, whereas fourteen databases provide institutional data (indicators based on social policy legislation). Six databases include data on the number of beneficiaries, whereas only one infrastructure provides a platform for tax and benefit microsimulations. Three databases provide access to micro level data in terms of comparative socio-economic or income surveys. Several databases are comprised of different types of data.

We also mapped the policy programs that are included in the different databases. We distinguished between cash benefits (family benefits, unemployment benefits, sickness benefits, pensions, work accident insurance, social assistance, and disability/invalidity/survivors benefits) and public services (child care, health care, elder care and active labor market policy). Only one database covers the entire social policy system, including both cash and in-kind benefits in their many forms. Notably, this database is based on social expenditures and organised by the OECD.

Most databases cover developments in cash benefits, albeit chief focus often is on distinct parts of the cash benefit system, such as family benefits or out-of-work benefits. Only one database lacks data on cash benefits. By comparison, public services are less well covered. Nine databases lack data on public services. It is somewhat more common among the different data infrastructures to cover developments in family benefits, unemployment benefits, pensions and social assistance, compared with developments in sickness benefits, work-accidents insurance or disability/invalidity/survivors

benefits. In terms of public services, child care and health care are more commonly in focus than elder care and active labor market policy.

Although availability and access to comparative data for social policy analysis has improved considerably in recent decades, increased efforts are necessary in order to keep existing data infrastructures up to date and to expand data collection to areas where comparative social policy data are lacking. Particularly, several databases would benefit by an inclusion of public services, which would facilitate more in depth analyses of the interplay between cash and care in the reorganisation of the European welfare states. Although access to expenditure data on public services seems to be feasible, we still lack good quality social policy indicators on the institutional structure of child care, elder care, health care and active labor market policy. It is nowadays often recognised that welfare state analyses increasingly need to rely on different types of data to more accurately assess the driving forces and consequences of social policy. However, in order to move this multidimensional perspective on social policy analysis beyond developments in cash benefits, we need to better integrate public service provision in data infrastructures for the comparative analysis of welfare states.

There are only rare examples of studies that have sought to combine different kinds of data in order to generate a more complete and nuanced picture of the workings of the welfare state. Part of this omission is likely to be directly related to the proliferation of various data collection efforts that have been described in this report. The differences in definitions, scope and format between data infrastructures complicate research with integrative ambitions. Increased communication between data managers as well as efforts towards harmonisation may provide a fruitful way forward to improve also the possibilities of researchers to combine data from various sources, even though it should be recognised that some databases serve specific research questions requiring a distinct set of definitions and indicators. Increased cooperation between research infrastructures could also have synergic effects by strengthening data quality and promoting better use of resources devoted to the collection of comparable social policy data.

appendix 1

Table a1.1 Overview of databases included in the inventory

Name	Countries	Years	Type	Programs	Homepage
ASPIRE	120 countries (mostly low- and middle-income countries)	1998-2014	Expenditure, beneficiaries	Family benefits, unemployment benefits, pensions, work-accidents, social assistance, disability/invalidity/survivors benefits	http://datatopics.worldbank.org/aspire/
BenWage	OECD	2001-2016	Institutional	Family benefits, unemployment benefits, social assistance	http://www.oecd.org/social/benefits-and-wages.htm
CFPD	OECD18, Greece, Luxembourg, Portugal, Spain	1960-2010	Institutional	Family benefits	http://www.demogr.mpg.de/cgi-bin/databases/fampoldb/index.plx
CWED	EU27, Australia, Japan, New Zealand, South Korea, Taiwan, the United States	1971-2011	Institutional	Unemployment benefits, sickness benefits, pensions, work-accidents	http://cwed2.org/
CWS	OECD18, Greece, Luxembourg, Portugal, Spain	1960-2012	Expenditure, institutional	Family benefits, unemployment benefits, pensions, social assistance, disability/invalidity/survivors benefits, health care, active labor market policy	http://www.unc.edu/~jdsteph/common/data-common.html
DICE	EU28, Australia, Canada, Japan, New Zealand, Norway, Switzerland, the United States	1975-2015	Expenditure, institutional	Social assistance, child care, family benefits, pensions, health care	http://www.cesifo-group.de/ifoHome/facts/DICE.html
EU-SILC	EU28, Iceland, Norway, Switzerland, Turkey	2004-2016	Socio-economic survey	Family benefits, unemployment benefits, sickness benefits, pensions, work-accidents, social assistance, disability/invalidity, survivors benefits, child care	http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/microdata/european-union-statistics-on-income-and-living-conditions
FPD	OECD	1995-2014	Expenditure, institutional, beneficiaries	Family benefits, child care	http://www.oecd.org/social/family/database.htm
GGP	Australia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russian Federation, Sweden	1960-2008	Expenditure, institutional	Pensions, unemployment benefits, childcare, health care, family allowances.	http://www.ggp-i.org/data/ggp-contextual-database
GHO	194 countries	1995-2014	Expenditure, institutional	Health care	http://www.who.int/gho/en/
ESSPROS	EU28, Iceland, Norway, Serbia, Switzerland, Turkey	1990-2014	Expenditure, beneficiaries	Sickness/health care, disability, old age, survivors, family/children, unemployment, housing, social exclusion.	http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/social-protection/overview

Name	Countries	Years	Type	Programs	Homepage
LIS	66 countries spanning all continents	1967-2013	Income survey	Family benefits, unemployment benefits, sickness benefits, pensions, work-accidents, social assistance, disability/invalidity, survivors benefits	http://www.lisdatacenter.org/our-data/
CSB-MIPI	EU27, United States for later waves	1992, 2001, 2009, 2012	Institutional	Family benefits, pensions, social assistance, housing allowance, tax credits, in-work benefits, minimum wages, income guarantee for the elderly	http://www.centrumvoorsociaalbeleid.be/index.php?q=node/3270
Multilinks	EU27, Norway, Georgia, Russia	2004, 2009	Institutional	Family benefits, child care, elder care	https://multilinks-database.wzb.eu/
NowBASE	Denmark, Faroe Islands, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden	1995-2013	Expenditure, beneficiaries	Family benefits, sickness benefits, pensions, social assistance, disability/invalidity/survivors benefits, health care, elder care	http://nowbase.org/da
SSI	104 countries spanning all continents		Expenditure, institutional	Family benefits, unemployment benefits, sickness benefits, pensions, work-accidents, social assistance, disability/invalidity, survivors benefits, health care	http://www.ilo.org/dyn/ilossi/ssimain.home
EUROMOD	EU28, Iceland, Norway, Switzerland, Turkey	1998-2015	Microsimulation	Family benefits, unemployment benefits, sickness benefits, pensions, work-accidents, social assistance, disability/invalidity, survivors benefits, child care	https://www.euromod.ac.uk/
EUROMOD – HHoT	EU28, Iceland, Norway, Switzerland, Turkey	2009-2015	Microsimulation	Family benefits, unemployment benefits, sickness benefits, pensions, work-accidents, social assistance, disability/invalidity, survivors benefits, child care	https://www.euromod.ac.uk/
Health	OECD, Brazil, China, Colombia, Costa Rica, India, Indonesia, Lithuania, Russia, South Africa	1960-2015	Expenditure	Health care	http://www.oecd.org/els/health-systems/health-data.htm
PAG	OECD	2007-2015	Institutional, expenditure	Old-age and survivors benefits	http://www.oecd-ilibrary.org/social-issues-migration-health/data/oecd-pensions-statistics/pensions-at-a-glance-2011_data-00625-en?isPartOf=/content/datacollection/pension-data-en

Name	Countries	Years	Type	Programs	Homepage
SHARE	Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland	2004-2013	Socio-economic survey (focused on health)	Family benefits, sickness benefits, unemployment benefits, pensions, work-accidents, social assistance, disability/invalidity/survivors benefits	http://www.share-project.org/
SOCX	OECD	1980-2016	Expenditure	Family benefits, unemployment benefits, sickness benefits, pensions, work-accidents, social assistance, disability/invalidity, survivors benefits, child care, health care, elder care, active labor market policy	https://www.oecd.org/social/expenditure.htm
SOCR	OECD, Bulgaria, Cyprus, Latvia, Lithuania, Malta, Romania	2007-2012	Beneficiaries	Unemployment benefits, pensions, social assistance, disability/invalidity, survivors benefits	http://www.oecd.org/social/recipients.htm
SPIN	OECD, EU27, Indonesia, Philippines, Taiwan, Thailand, Vietnam, Brazil	1930-2015	Institutional	Family benefits, unemployment benefits, sickness benefits, pensions, work-accidents, social assistance	http://www.sofi.su.se/spin/
EC Tax Benefit	EU28	2001-2015	Institutional	Family benefits, unemployment benefits, social assistance	http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/db_indicators/tax_benefits_indicators/index_en.htm

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InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

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More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.be

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Inclusive Growth Research
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